

Plagiarism Policy

In this course, you will collaborate with other students during activities and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own assignments, presentations, and papers, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with Harvard academic policy. You can read the guidelines on the Harvard College handbook for students here: <https://handbook.fas.harvard.edu/book/academic-integrity>

COVID-19 NOTE: I recognize that we are living through a global pandemic and that as a result there may be points during the semester when you are unable to meet class deadlines. I am giving each of you 2 “grace days” to use as you see fit over the course of the semester. Each grace day offers a full 24-hour extension and can be used for any assignment except the final research presentation. You will need to email me in advance of the assignment due date to let me know that you will be using a grace day, but you do not need to explain or justify its use. **If you use up all of your grace days and you need an extension for an emergency reason (illness, family or personal issues, etc.) please email me or visit me during office hours;** given the events of the past year and a half I am inclined to be flexible. The same thing goes for absences during in-person discussion/activities or remote discussion/activities.

Grading Structure

Note: All formal written assignments for this course should conform to the Written Assignments Guidelines distributed on the first day of class and available on the class website.

Engagement (20%): Whatever the format, being an engaged member of this class means that you will regularly contribute to discussion, including asking questions, responding to others' questions, offering and defending your own opinions, and generally helping move the class towards new levels of understanding without dominating the discussion. Your overall course engagement will receive a single grade based on the following criteria: absent for more than five in-person classes or remote equivalents (0 pts), passive (10 pts), occasionally active (15 pts), or regularly active (20 pts). If you are having issues with accruing multiple absences for emergency reasons, please contact me to let me know—see the COVID-19 note above.

Short Response Papers (15% each): Each paper will ask you to respond to a prompt that addresses a major issue pertaining to one course unit. These short response papers will be between 1000–1200 words. You will not be required to do additional outside reading; instead, you will be asked to critically evaluate and synthesize concepts and evidence drawn from readings, lectures, and activities. Prompts will be provided ≥ 1 week in advance of due dates.

Final Research Presentation (5%): Your final research presentation will occur during the last week of class. During your presentation you will share an overview of your final research paper with the class. Guidelines for your final research presentation will be distributed by Week 10.

Final Research Paper (30%): The research paper provides you with an opportunity to explore some aspect of inequality in the human past in greater depth. If there is a period, region, or dimension of inequality that has always fascinated you, this is your chance to learn more

about it through engaging with the archaeological literature. Detailed guidelines for the final research paper will be presented by Week 7. You will submit a short research paper proposal to Dr Beck by Week 11.

Papers should be submitted by email to jbeck1@fas.harvard.edu. They are to be submitted by midnight on the due date. For example, the first short paper for this class should be submitted by midnight on Friday, October 1, meaning that you will have all day Friday to work on it if you choose. Late assignments will be docked by one point for the first 24 hours, then two points per each subsequent day. See the COVID-19 Note on p.2 for information about grace days and extensions.

ASSIGNMENT DUE DATES

Assignment (% Final Grade)	Due Date
Short Response Paper 1 (15%)	Friday, October 1
Short Response Paper 2 (15%)	Friday, October 29
Research Paper Proposal (5%)	Wednesday, November 10
Short Response Paper 3 (15%)	Wednesday, November 23
Final Research Presentation (5%)	Tuesday, November 30*
Final Research Paper (25%)	Thursday, December 2

*Depending on class enrolment, final research presentations may extend to Thursday, December 2nd if scheduling requires.

Class Schedule and Reading List

Note: The readings should be read before the day on which they are listed to ensure that you are prepared for the lecture, discussion, and activities. I reserve the right to change the readings if I feel it is pertinent to the direction of the course; readings would be exchanged rather than added.

Week 1: Introduction

Thursday, September 2

Topic: Introduction to course

Readings: Graeber & Wengrow 2018

UNIT I: Tipping the Scales

Week 2: What is inequality & how can archaeologists assess it?

Tuesday, September 7

Topic: What is inequality?

Readings: Afonso, Lafleur & Alarcón 2015; Kohler et al. 2017

Optional Reading: Krieger & Davey Smith 2004

Thursday, September 9

Topic: Introduction to archaeological approaches

Readings: Renfrew & Bahn 2018, Chapter 2

Activity: *Material traces of inequality*

Week 3: Measuring Inequality

Tuesday, September 14

Topic: Analyzing inequality data

Readings: No readings—fill out and submit your assignment in preparation for this class.

Thursday, September 16

Topic: How have past scholars thought about inequality and human social change?

Readings: Trigger 2008

Week 4: Hunting and gathering

Tuesday, September 21

Topic: Hunting and gathering

Readings: Kelly 1995 Preface & Chapter 1; Lee 1979 excerpt

Thursday, September 23

Topic: Scale, complexity, and inequality in hunter-gatherer groups

Readings: Dietrich et al., 2012; Ortmann & Kidder 2012

Week 5: Horticulture and pastoralism

Tuesday, September 28

Topic: Coalition and consensus in hunter-gatherer and forager-farmer societies + discussion of written assignment guidelines

Readings: Angelbeck 2016; Henry & Barrier 2016

UNIT II: Scaling up?

Thursday, September 30

Topic: On the hoof—introduction to pastoralism

Readings: McCabe 1990

Week 6: Pastoralism and agriculture

Tuesday, October 5

Topic: Pastoralism and inequality

Readings: Wright 2013; Arbuckle 2012

Thursday, October 7

Topic: Subsistence transitions

Readings: Diamond 1987; Antrosio 2011; Wyman 2020 (podcast)

Week 7: Emerging inequalities

Tuesday, October 12

Topic: Farmers in flux

Readings: Price 1995; Wright 2014

Thursday, October 14

Topic: Production, inheritance, and inequality + final research paper guidelines

Readings: Alden Smith et al. 2010

Week 8: Early complex societies and elites

Tuesday, October 19

Topic: Introduction to early complex societies

Readings: Gilman 1981

Activity: *Decision-making and scalar stress*

Thursday, October 21

Topic: Commodity and control: political-economic approaches to power

Readings: Earle et al. 2015

Guest: *Dr Colin Quinn (Hamilton College)*

Week 9: Are elites optional?

Tuesday, October 26

Topic: Elites make the world go round

Readings: Beck 2006

Thursday, October 28

Topic: Copper Age Iberia: Aggregations and monumentality without elites

Readings: Beck 2020

UNIT III: The familiar

Week 10: Introducing states and empires

Tuesday, November 2

Topic: Introducing states + final presentation guidelines

Readings: Green 2020; Wyman 2021 (podcast)

Thursday, November 4

Topic: Introducing empires

Readings: Sinopoli 2001

Week 11: Power and control

Tuesday, November 9

Topic: Labor, infrastructure & inequality

Readings: Wilkinson 2019

Optional reading: Becker 2020

Thursday, November 11

Topic: Imperial power

Readings: Morrison and Lycett 1994

Activity: *Campus-based activity*

Week 12: Partitioning power and evading the state

Tuesday, November 16

Topic: Partitioning power

Readings: Green 2021

Optional reading: Fargher et al. 2010

Guest: *Dr Adam Green (University of Cambridge)*

Thursday, November 18

Topic: Evading the state: shatter zones and peripheries

Video: Scott 2010

Readings: Raffield 2021

Optional reading: Galaty 2013

Week 13: Are there alternatives?

Thursday, November 25

Topic: Essential tensions: inequality and alternatives

Readings: Borck 2018, Quinn & Beck 2016

NOVEMBER 25–29 THANKSGIVING BREAK

Week 14: Conclusions and student presentations

Thursday, December 2

Topic: Class conclusions

Readings: None

Reading List

- Afonso, H., LaFleur, M. & Alarcón, D. (2015). Concepts of inequality. *Development Issues*, 1, 1-2. <https://www.un.org/development/desa/dpad/publication/no-1-concepts-of-inequality/>
- Alden Smith, E., Borgerhoff Mulder, M., Bowles, S., Gurven, M., Hertz, T., & Shenk, M. (2010). Production systems, inheritance and inequality in premodern societies: Conclusions. *Current Anthropology*, 51(1), 85-94. <https://doi.org/10.1086/649029>
- Angelbeck, B. (2016). The balance of autonomy and alliance in anarchic societies: the organization of defences in the Coast Salish past. *World Archaeology*, 48(1), 51-69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00438243.2015.1131620>
- Antrosio, J. (2011, June 1). *Agriculture: Jared Diamond's worst mistake?* Living Anthropologically. <https://www.livinganthropologically.com/archaeology/agriculture-worst-mistake/>
- Arbuckle, B. S. (2012). Pastoralism, provisioning, and power at Bronze Age Acemhöük, Turkey. *American Anthropologist*, 114(3), 462-476. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1548-1433.2012.01446.x>
- Beck, J. (2020). The labor of building a community: Exploring the divergent trajectories of complex sites in Copper Age Iberia. *American Anthropologist*, 122(4), 896-901. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13498>
- Beck Jr., R. A. (2006). Persuasive politics and domination at Moundville and Cahokia. In B. M. Butler & P. D. Welch (Eds.), *Leadership and Polity in Mississippian Society* (pp. 19-42). Southern Illinois University at Carbondale Center for Archaeological Investigations, Occasional Paper no. 33.
- Becker, S. K. (2020). Why heterarchy? A view from the Tiwanaku state's (AD 500–1100) labor force. *American Anthropologist*, 122(4), 934–939. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13499>
- Borck, L. (2018). Constructing the future history: Prefiguration as historical epistemology and the chronopolitics of archaeology. *Journal of Contemporary Archaeology*, 5(2), 229-238. <https://doi.org/10.1558/jca.33560>
- Diamond, J. (1987). The worst mistake in the history of the human race. *Discover*, 91-93.
- Dietrich, O., Heun, M., Notroff, J., Schmidt, K. & Zarnkow, M. (2012). The role of cult and feasting in the emergence of Neolithic communities. New evidence from Göbekli Tepe, south-eastern Turkey. *Antiquity*, 86(333), 674-695. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00047840>
- Earle, T., Ling, J., Uhnér, C., Stos-Gale, Z., & Melheim, L. (2015). The political economy and metal trade in Bronze Age Europe: Understanding regional variability in terms of comparative advantages and articulations. *European Journal of Archaeology*, 18(4), 633-657. <https://doi.org/10.1179/1461957115y.0000000008>
- Fargher, L., Blanton, R., & Heredia Espinoza, V. (2010) Egalitarian ideology and political power in prehispanic Central Mexico: The case of Tlaxcallan. *Latin American Antiquity*, 21(3): 227-251. <https://doi.org/10.7183/1045-6635.21.3.227>
- Galaty, M. L. (2013). "An offense to honor is never forgiven . . .": Violence and landscape archaeology in highland northern Albania. In S. Ralph (Ed.), *The Archaeology of Violence: Interdisciplinary Approaches* (pp. 143-157). State University of New York Press.
- Gilman, A. (1981). The development of social stratification in Bronze Age Europe. *Current Anthropology*, 22(1): 1-23. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/2742414>

- Graeber, D., & Wengrow, D. (2018). How to change the course of human history. *Eurozine*.
<https://www.eurozine.com/change-course-human-history/>
- Green, A. (2020). Debt and inequality: Comparing the “means of specification” in the early cities of Mesopotamia and the Indus civilization. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 60, 101232.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2020.101232>
- Green, A. (2021). Killing the priest-king: Addressing egalitarianism in the Indus civilization. *Journal of Archaeological Research*, 29, 153-202. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-020-09147-9>
- Henry, E. R., & Barrier, C. R. (2016). The organization of dissonance in Adena-Hopewell societies of eastern North America. *World Archaeology*, 48(1), 87-109.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00438243.2015.1132175>
- Kelly, R. L. (2013). Hunter-gatherers and anthropology. In *The Lifeways of Hunter-Gatherers: The Foraging Spectrum*, (2nd ed., pp. 1-37). Cambridge University Press.
- Kohler, T., Smith, M. E., Bogaard, A., Feinman, G. M., Peterson, C. E., Betzenhauser, A., Pailles, M., Stone, E. C., Prentiss A., Dennehy, T. J., Ellyson, L. J., Nicholas, L. M., Fauseit, R. K., Styring, A., Whitlam, J., Fochesato, M., Foor, T. A., & Bowles, S. (2017). Greater post-Neolithic wealth disparities in Eurasia than in North America and Mesoamerica. *Nature*, 551, 619-622.
<https://doi:10.1038/nature24646>
- Krieger, N., & Davey Smith, G. (2004). “Bodies count,” and body counts: Social epidemiology and embodying inequality. *Epidemiologic Reviews*, 26, 92-103.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/epirev/mxh009>
- Lee, R. B. (1979). Hunting as a life’s work + hunting success and status differences, In *The !Kung San: Men, Women, and Work in a Foraging Society* (pp. 242–249). Cambridge University Press.
- McCabe, J. T. (1990). Turkana pastoralism: A case against the tragedy of the commons. *Human Ecology*, 18(1), 81-103. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4602953>
- Morrison, K., & Lycett, M. (1994). Centralized power, centralized authority? Ideological claims and archaeological patterns. *Asian Perspectives*, 33(2), 327-350.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/42928325>
- Ortmann, A. L., & Kidder, T. R. (2012). Building Mound A at Poverty Point, Louisiana: Monumental public architecture, ritual practice, and implications for hunter-gatherer complexity. *Geoarchaeology*, 28, 66-86. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gea.21430>
- Quinn, C., & Beck, J. (2016). Essential tensions: A framework for exploring inequality through mortuary archaeology and bioarchaeology. *Open Archaeology* 2: 18-41. <https://doi.org/10.1515/opar-2016-0002>
- Raffield, B. (2021). Broken worlds: Towards an archaeology of the shatter zone. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-021-09520-y>
- Renfrew, C., & Bahn, P. (2018). What is left? The variety of the evidence. In *Archaeology Essentials: Theory/Methods/Practice*. (4th ed., pp.38-61). Thames & Hudson.
- Scott, J. (2010, November 4). *The art of not being governed* [Video]. The MacMillan Report, Yale University. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aVwrUsib4vU>
- Sinopoli C.M. (2001). Empires. In G.M.Feinman & T.D. Price (Eds.), *Archaeology at the Millennium* (pp.439–471), Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-72611-3_13

- Trigger, B. G. (2008). Evolutionary archaeology. In *A History of Archaeological Thought*. (2nd Ed., pp.166-210). Cambridge University Press.
- Wilkinson, D. (2020). Infrastructure and inequality: An archaeology of the Inka road through the Amaybamba cloud forests. *Journal of Social Archaeology*, 19(1), 27-46.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1469605318822551>
- Wright, J. (2013). Inequality on the surface: Horses, power, and community in the Mongolian Bronze Age. In B. Arbuckle & S. McCart (Eds.), *Animals and Inequality in the Ancient World* (pp. 275-293). University Press of Colorado. <https://doi.org/10.5876/9781607322863.c013>
- Wright, K.I. (2014). Domestication and inequality? Households, corporate groups and food processing tools at Neolithic Çatalhöyük. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*, 33, 1–33. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2013.09.007>
- Wyman, P. (Host). (2020, September 10). The first farmers [Audio podcast episode]. In *Tides of History*. Wondery. <https://wondery.com/shows/tides-of-history/episode/5629-the-first-farmers/>
- Wyman, P. (Host). (2021, July 29). Cities, states, and living in ancient Mesopotamia [Audio podcast episode]. In *Tides of History*. Wondery. <https://wondery.com/shows/tides-of-history/episode/5629-cities-states-and-living-in-ancient-mesopotamia/>